

Rugged, Durable, Industrial-grade Bluetooth Beacon

摘要: Rugged and durable BLE beacon for location, temperature, and acceleration monitoring in industrial applications.

Are you still seeking a suitable location beacon with sensors for your industrial applications? How about learning more details about our P1 Plus Robust Beacon for having an additional choice? P1 Plus is a Bluetooth LE beacon leveraging the nRF52 series chip and equipped with a temperature sensor and an accelerometer.

We have welcomed the pre-order some time ago. It is encouraging that the P1 Plus has lived up to the expectations of Minew and our customers in real-world applications. It has made full use of its innovation.

"I installed P1 Plus on the wall of my cold storage. I was very satisfied and surprised that it was able to maintain excellent operation in a -15°C environment". An anonymous customer recently sent us feedback.

Durability is the nature of the P1 Plus. To perform well in some harsh industrial conditions, such as food storage with ultra-low temperature or some chemical plants with high temperature, the P1 Plus is innovated with extraordinary protection grade and hardware quality.

Reliable water-resistance

The P1 Plus can tolerate a humid environment.

The P1 Plus is IP68 waterproof, which has been laboratory tested to work in some humid locations. Moreover, the tight sealing of P1 Plus also strengthens its waterproof performance. If you want to use the P1 Plus in a cold room or a freezer, it is just right for you.

Rare shock resistance

P1 Plus is likely to remain intact even if bumped or dropped.

The IK09 level of shock resistance makes the P1 Plus defend against certain collisions or drops during the transportation and storage of materials in the warehousing and logistics industry. The rare shock resistance helps users to control the cost of replacing and maintaining the device.

Temperature monitoring and wide operating temperature

The high precision temperature sensor allows the P1 Plus to monitor the ambient temperature in real-time. Cooperated with the Cloud Platform (further developed by software company), users can remotely monitor the temperature of the venue.

The P1 Plus device itself has a maximum operating temperature range of -40°C to 85°C , enabling monitoring of tough environments. The exact temperature range will vary from how the device is developed based on customer requirements as well as how the P1 Plus product is installed.

Keep track of every movement

The P1 Plus is equipped with an accelerometer that makes it possible to monitor the position of tagged items in real-time. When you mount the P1 Plus on your container or storage box, you can get the location of these items according to the development software (provided by the software vendor). The real-time and precise location allows you to optimize space occupancy, material utilization, and prevent asset loss.

**P1 version is also available, without temperature sensor and accelerometer.*

Multiple and stable mounting options

With two mounting ears, the P1 Plus is designed to facilitate the user to fix the device to the target item with screws for great robustness. For example, on wooden boxes, on walls, on pillars, and much more with a hard surface. Also, the P1 Plus can be fixed directly using double-sided adhesive, providing a solution for some situations where screws cannot be used. It is important to note that the recommended operating temperature range is -40°C to 85°C when using screws, and 10°C to 75°C when using double-sided adhesive. This is a technical recommendation in order to effectively use and not to damage the device.

Smart switch preventing accidental shutdown

To prevent the P1 Plus from being accidentally shut down during transit and in actual use, our engineers designed to use the magnetic switch. Simply put the magnetic sheeting close to the device and the blue light will be on for 3 seconds, which means successful turned on. Similarly, hold the magnetic sheeting close to the device, the blue light will be on for 5 seconds for a successful shutdown.

Battery life is what you'll be surprised

P1 Plus is equipped with an industrial-grade lithium battery with a 1200mAh capacity. The advantage of battery replaceable allows P1 Plus to greatly reduce the operating cost for users. There is no need to replace the entire device but the battery to extend the life of the device. The default battery life is up to 44 months, providing endurance support for more possibilities. A flashing red light means low battery and remains users to replace the battery in time to avoid losses due to power depletion.

You can also configure more about the P1 Plus based on our provided App SDK. Make it yours.

The value that the P1 Plus can provide to businesses and the specific scenarios in which it can be used can be viewed in our another article, [A Latest Location Beacon - P1 Plus, Made for Durability](#). Or you can also browse directly to the [P1 Plus details](#), which also displays information on how it works and its parameters. You can order the P1 Plus now. So, why not find a trustworthy Bluetooth LE beacon for your special and tough applications as soon as possible?

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